

Energy sharing through Energy Communities: Where are we and where are we headed?

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What is an energy community?

- Formal definition
 - EU Renewable energy community
 - EU Citizen energy community
- Informal definition
 - Any collection of residents, or companies with energy assets that want to work together.
- Alternatives
 - Community choice aggregator (CCA, adjust input mixture)
 - Aggregator (typically wholesale)
 - Peer-to-Peer (P2P)

Source: Eichman et al., (2022) <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15062016>

DSO= distribution system operator
EC = Energy community

What is an energy community?

- Many European consumers can produce their own energy under “self-consumption” rules
- They may also be able to sell excess energy
- Collective self-consumption lets a consumer trade energy with neighbors
- Example:
 - Retail €280/MWh
 - Wholesale €60/MWh

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Why share energy energy?

- Green transition
- Autonomy
- Economic savings
- Energy savings
- Equity
- Empowerment

Individual self-consumption Collective self-consumption

Electricity transmission network

Challenges?

- Investment Capital
 - Credits, incentives, tariffs, etc.
- Distributing energy between parties
 - Dynamic distribution coefficients
 - Previously, this limited the ability of an EC to trade with neighbors
 - Maximizing benefit is not easy for ECs
- How to select assets?
- How to size assets and distribute across prosumers?

Source: Eichman et al., (2022) ECOS 2022 proceedings

What kind of communities and do we want?

- We can implicitly or explicitly make this decision, but...
- The result is dependent on the path you choose to get there.

Measures		Strategy 1 Single metered Consumer	Strategy 2 Multiple metered Consumers	Strategy 3 Supplier+ Consumers	Strategy 4 Supplier+ Producer+ Consumers	Strategy 5 DSO+ Supplier+ Producer+ Consumers
Market Measures	Wholesale market access	0	1	1	2	2
	Local flexibility markets	1	2	2	2	2
	Capacity markets	0	0	0	2	2
	Multi-sector markets	1	1	2	2	2
Regulatory, Legal and organizational strategies	Enable P2P trading	2	2	1	1	0
	Enable aggregation	2	2	1	1	1
	Tax credits and incentives	1	1	1	1	1
	Self-consumption	2	2	1	1	0
	Strong local community	2	2	1	1	0

Source: Eichman et al., (2022) <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15062016>

Cooperative Energy Markets

- One example:
Developed a
implementation
based on Nash
Bargaining

Thank you for your attention

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Methodology: Scenario development

1. Load Only

2. Load + Photovoltaic panels (PV)
(no export)

3. Load + PV
(with export)

4. Load + PV + Batt.
(no export)

5. Load + PV + Batt.
(with export)

Scenarios include:

- Collective self-consumption (with and w/o)
- Export (with and w/o)
- 5 retail rates (see backup for details)
- 2 equipment distributions (see backup for details)
- 2 sizes (see backup for details)

Scenario combinations

Item	Device configurations	Collective self-consumption	Renewable sales (export)	Retail Rates	Equipment distribution	Size
1	Load only	Yes, No	Yes, No	5	Distributed, centralized	Large, Small
2	Load + PV	Yes, No	Yes, No	5	Distributed, centralized	Large, Small
3	Load + PV + Battery	Yes, No	Yes, No	5	Distributed, centralized	Large, Small

Device assumptions

Parameter	Value
PV capital cost	\$1387/kW [1]
PV fixed operation & maintenance cost	\$10/kW-year [1]
Storage capital cost	\$955/kWh [1]
Storage energy capacity	4 hours at rated discharge power
Storage efficiency	85% AC to AC
Storage self-discharge	1% of stored energy per day [2]

Financial assumptions

Parameter	Value
Euro to dollar	0.89
Study period	20 years
Tax rate	25%
Equity	41.9%
Interest rate on debt	3.125% [3]
Inflation	1.6%
WACC	7%
Depreciation schedule	10% for up to 20 years [4]

1. IRENA, "Renewable Power Generation Costs in 2020," International Renewable Energy Agency, Abu Dhabi, 2021.
2. E. Redondo-Iglesias, P. Venet, and S. Pelissier, "Measuring Reversible and Irreversible Capacity Losses on Lithium-Ion Batteries," in 2016 IEEE Vehicle Power and Propulsion Conference (VPPC), Hangzhou, China, Oct. 2016, pp. 1–5. doi: 10.1109/VPPC.2016.7791723.
3. Banco de España, "Table of banks' lending and borrowing rates." https://clientebancario.bde.es/pcb/en/menu-horizontal/productoservici/relacionados/tiposinteres/guia-textual/tiposinteresprac/Tabla_de_tipos__a0b053c69a40f51.html.
4. infoautónomos, "¿Qué son las amortizaciones? ¿Cómo funcionan? Ejemplo." <https://www.infoautonomos.com/contabilidad/tablas-de-amortizacion-para-los-bienes-de-una-empresa/>.

Community description

- The community is comprised of 8 members (see table for more information)
- Location is based on weather data, workday calendar, and PV generation from Barcelona, Spain.
- Data is developed using the LoadProfileGenerator†

† Noah Pflugradt, *LoadProfileGenerator*. 2022. [Online]. <https://www.loadprofilegenerator.de/>

#	Identifier (CHR)	Description	Max. Power (kW)	Min. Power (kW)	Avg. Power (kW)	StDev of Power (kW)
1	01	Couple both at work	6.59	0.103	0.617	0.792
2	05	Family with 3 children, both parents work	3.76	0.045	0.594	0.589
3	07	Working single person	3.94	0.046	0.205	0.370
4	15	Multigenerational family with 2 working adults, 2 children and 2 seniors	7.82	0.100	1.382	1.233
5	16	Couple over 65 years old	5.49	0.017	0.584	0.795
6	22	Single working woman with 1 child	2.10	0.055	0.213	0.285
7	40	Non-working couple (30-64 years old)	3.00	0.062	0.406	0.439
8	52	Student sharing an apartment	4.08	0.052	0.426	0.489

RECOMMIT

Reenvisioning the potential of energy communities

Applications

- Multi-market optimization
- Hydrogen business case assessment
- Wholesale market revenue comparison
- Retail rate optimization
- Solar PV + Storage
- Real-time optimization control of electrolyzer
- Vehicle fleet optimization

Device and Financial assumptions

Device assumptions

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Storage capital cost	\$955/kWh [1]
Storage energy capacity	4 hours at rated discharge power
Storage efficiency	85% AC to AC
Storage self-discharge	1% of stored energy per day [2]
Retail electricity rates	Sale price based on wholesale market price [3] Endesa (One Luz and One Luz 3 period) [4,5] Hola Luz (Classic and Fair rate) [6] Pepe Energy (ECO) [7]

Financial assumptions

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Sizing and location breakdown

- PV size for small systems is based on 75% of average load at site
- PV size for large systems is based on 50% of max. load at site
- Storage size for small systems is based on 20% of average load
- Storage size for large systems is based on 20% of max load at site

PV sizing and location

Location	Size	Consumer							
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Distributed	Small	0.5	0.4	0.2	1.0	0.4	0.2	0.3	0.3
Concentrated	Small		1.6	1.7					
Distributed	Large	3.3	1.9	2.0	3.9	2.7	1.1	1.5	2.0
Concentrated	Large		9.0	9.4					

Storage sizing and location

Location	Size	Consumer							
		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Distributed	Small	0.12	0.1	0.0	0.28	0.12	0.04	0.08	0.09
Concentrated	Small		0.4	0.5					
Distributed	Large	1.3	0.8	0.8	1.6	1.1	0.4	0.6	0.8
Concentrated	Large		3.6	3.8					

Results

- Collective self-consumption (CSC) with export is the least cost
- Generally, collective self-consumption (no export) is better than self-consumption (SC) with export.
- Large systems were preferred
- Distributed systems have lower operating cost than concentrated systems

CSC: Collective self-consumption
 SC: Individual self-consumption

Dist.: Distributed
 Concen.: Concentrated

Motivation

- European energy goals seek to **reduce consumption, increase efficiency and increase renewable shares.**
- **Energy communities** can help to address the European goals
- **Clean Energy for All Europeans Package (CEP)** creates a framework for energy communities, amongst other things
- Expansion of **Spanish framework** for energy communities and **incentives**
 - RD 477/2021: €1.12 billion for self-consumption and storage
- Limited literature comparing community coordination strategies including **Collective Self-Consumption (CSC)** in Spain
- Current literature does not include recent **updates to CSC rules** in Spain
 - Hourly variable distribution coefficient

Authors

Energy Systems Analytics is a research group whose areas of expertise are Statistical Analysis & Data Visualization, Modelling & Optimization, and Sustainability & Economic Assessment. Group scientific activity focuses on Energy System Integration and Innovative Energy Uses. Our technological research fields are:

